

TURKISH PARENTS' PERCEPTION OF EDUCATION: EXPECTATIONS AND IDEALS

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to reveal the educational perceptions and expectations of the Turkish parents. For this purpose, interviews were conducted with 49 parents who had students in preschool, primary, secondary and high school in Siirt and Batman. The research is a qualitative phenomenological study. Interviews were conducted using semi-structured interview form to collect detailed data from parents. Interview form questions were determined by pre-interview with teachers and school administrators and developed by academicians who were experts in the field. The data were analyzed by descriptive analysis technique and expressed in tables. Research findings are given below.

When it is asked the question of “Why education?”, the parents mostly mentioned the issues that education supports economic, cultural returns and individual development. For the question, “What kind of Education” all of the parents mentioned educational practices appropriate to contemporary education approaches and mentioned various aspects of contemporary education components. For the question of “Will your children continue their education after compulsory education if the level of your economic welfare is well?” the majority of the parents stated that education is obligatory under all circumstances and that their children will continue their education due to socio-cultural and economic benefits. Seven parents stated that they would leave the choice to the student because volunteering is necessary to get efficiency. Related to “Course selection” more than half of the parents preferred the courses that the students would encounter in their exams for their children and asked for the predominant courses to be given in the exam. Twelve parents emphasized the developmental courses appropriate to the ability of the students, while eight parents stated that all courses should be given. Related to “the future dream about their children and choice of department for higher education” more than half of the parents have dreams about their children; and stated that he would release the student in the department choices. Fourteen parents stated that they had not yet dreamed about the future and that they would decide the department with the

student. Ten parents stated that they had future dreams about their children and that they would not release their children in the selection of the department. In general, it was found that parents talked about an idealized education approach which refers to different components of contemporary education about how education should be, but as an expectation, they demanded an education which was formed with exam-oriented courses in order to provide socio-economic benefits.

Keywords: Parent, Education, Education Perception, Education Expectation.

1. Introduction

People dream the best life for his child and know that it can be through good education. This idea often leads to a desire to achieve the best possible education. This quest is a promising adventure on behalf of parents for our children to reach the education that we dream of -which we cannot reach. Yes, for every parent, the child should receive “good education, but what kind of education shapes this “good education” constitutes the fundamental problematic of many philosophical considerations. “All educational systems strive to produce effective citizens capable of participating in, and contributing to, their society” (Rubenstein, 2006). In fact, the parent's perception of education and the relative expectation of education may mean that it can create an overwhelming force on the child for the parent who has strengthened the child's ability to exercise his or her right to education. Therefore, the best use of this effective power can be seen as a great supporter on the way to the type, continuity and efficiency of the education the child will receive. In other words, the family is one of the most important determinants of the child's educational life. The family's perspective on education and support in this process is an indispensable necessity for the child.

It is a very important issue for the welfare of the society that parents can educate themselves and their children in the ways required by the information age and try to educate individuals who will apply education in every aspect of their lives (Güleş and Erişen, 2013). It is widely recognized in educational research that the educational expectations of parents and children are important factors in predicting children's educational achievements and occupational outcomes (Yu and Daraganova, 2015). Parents' expectations have received considerable attention in educational research to explain students' educational success in school (Zimmermann and Williams, 2016). Family expectations related to the child's education have a significant effect on the success of the child (Fan and Chen, 2001; Seginer, 1983; Hill and Taylor, 2004; Froiland and Davison, 2014; Smyth, 2018; Jacob and Wilder, 2010). It is known that the participation of families in the education process is effective and contributes to the socio-economic

development of the countries and helps to improve school-family cooperation. It is known that family participation in developed countries is given great importance and reflected in educational policies (Erdoğan and Demirkasımoğlu, 2010). Parental schooling expectations matters on the formation and transition of educational expectations for children learning (Delprato, 2019). In developing countries such as our country, education can be seen as a means of economic return and productivity (Coombs and Ahmed, 1974), but the main objective should be the multidimensional development of the individual and raising a healthy individual.

School, teacher and family should act in cooperation in the development of the student, preparing for life and realizing the educational goals (Çanak, 2013). In order for the education in schools to be successful and achieve its goals, the student needs the attention and assistance of their family (Ünal, et al., 2010). The educational expectations of both parents and children are determined by the social capital of the family and the similar educational expectations between parents and children facilitate the success of children (Hao and Bonstead-Bruns, 1998). In this respect, parents' expectation of education is a motivational and cultural factor that has a direct relationship with students' school performance (Mau, 1997). The educational expectations of families are a key focal point in the study of many educational phenomena in different socio-cultural contexts (Pons and Robine, 2013).

It can be argued that the basic determinants of individuals' educational beliefs are their educational philosophies (Altinkurt, et al., 2012). Accordingly, parents' expectations from education may differ from each other. In general, families try to give the child social adjustment, moral and moral value systems. The goal is; well-developed, healthy personalities and to train people who can express themselves well (Şimşek and Tanaydın, 2002). In this respect, the right and wrong approaches of the family towards their children should be determined through research in order to have a positive effect on the success of children (Babaoğlu, et al., 2018).

Parents' participation in educational processes and their being a complementary part of the school is very important for the child's educational life. In order to ensure the participation of parents in school processes, schools should support parents (Çanak, 2013). The impact of parental involvement on student academic achievement is acknowledged by teachers, administrators and policy makers who regard parental participation as an integral part of new educational reforms and initiatives (Wilder, 2014). Parental expectations of children's academic performance have been shown to positively correlate with children's grades, IQ scores, educational aspirations, and achievement motivation (Do and Mancillas, 2006).

An ideal school for parents is a school which takes into consideration the individual interests and abilities of the students, takes into consideration the artistic and sporting activities of the students, reveals their social development, gives importance to academic development with knowledge and equipment, effectively teaches at least one foreign language, entrusts children with confidence and provides rich material support (Nartgün and Kaya, 2016).

Parents expect to grow their children as an individual with characteristics such as self-confidence and responsibility, positively developed personality and character, equipped with the necessary knowledge to acquire a high quality high school, effective and socialized in communication among people, carrying the potential to acquire a good profession in the future, having religious, national and moral feelings, without harmful habits etc. (Can, 2015). Parents expect from schools to support their children's critical thinking skills and creativity by providing opportunities for students to investigate and question; they expect to create conditions that are open to innovations and equipped with technology and prepare the child for the future based on the understanding of student-centered education (Nartgün and Kaya, 2016). Therefore it can be claimed that the parents of low-achieving children had lower educational expectations of them and vice versa (Do and Mancillas, 2006).

The economic returns of education are prioritized by some parts of society. Education policy is preferred because it provides more comprehensive and functional solutions to reduce poverty. As the level of education increases, individuals have higher human capital equipment, work in jobs that require more qualifications, and earn higher earnings. The effect of education on reducing income and human poverty by increasing personal earnings and improving living standards has made education an important tool in the fight against poverty (Çokgezen and Erdene, 2015).

Considering the literature, it is possible to say that parents' expectations from education may be different. It is also known that parents' expectations are an important determinant of students' development and achievement. In this respect, the parents' educational perceptions and their expectations from education has an important place for educational policy.

1.1. Purpose of the Research

The aim of this study is to investigate the educational perceptions and expectations of parents who have students at preschool, primary, secondary and high schools. The problem sentences of the research prepared within this purpose are as follows:

1. Why do you want your child to receive education?
2. What kind of education do you want your child to receive?
3. If your welfare level was high, would you still have your child go on education after compulsory education? Or would you free your child to go to school or not? Why?
4. Which lessons do you think your child should take during the education process? Which courses should be given importance?
5. Do you have a future dream for your child? Would you release your child to choose a department at the university?

2. Method

In this section, research model, population and sample, data collection and analysis are given.

2.1. Research Model

This research is a phenomenological study designed with qualitative method. Yıldırım and Şimşek defines qualitative research as the type of research in which qualitative data collection methods such as observation, interview and document analysis are used, and a qualitative process for the realization of perceptions and events in a natural environment is followed.

In this research, data were analyzed by descriptive analysis method. Descriptive analysis is an analysis technique in which the data are summarized and interpreted according to the predetermined themes, direct quotations are frequently used in order to reflect the views of the individuals interviewed strikingly and the results are interpreted within the framework of cause-effect relationships.

2.2. Data Collection Tool

The data of this study were collected by interview with parents by using interview form questions prepared according to structured interview technique. In structured interview technique, the researcher prepares the questions in advance. These questions are asked to each participant within the framework of a certain system. Each participant is allowed to drill down

to ensure that they do not give the same answers at the interview where the same questions are asked.

For the interview form used in this research, media and related literature were scanned, structured draft interview form was prepared and interviews with teachers, parents and administrators were made and corrections determined on the questions were made. Afterwards, the structured interview form was examined by field experts and finalized and the interviews were conducted.

2.3. Study Group

The study group of the study consists of 49 parents with preschool, primary, secondary and high school students in Siirt and Batman province centers in 2016-2017 academic year. In order to determine the study group of the research, provinces that researcher can easily reach in terms of transportation were preferred. Table 1 presents the personal characteristics of the parents who participated in the study.

Table 1. Personal Characteristics of Participating Parents

Parents	Gender	Number of Child	Income Level	Education	Age
Parent (P1)	Male	6	1500 TL and -	High school	36-54
Parent (P2)	Male	1	3001 TL and	University	36-54
Parent (P3)	Male	4	1500 TL and	High school	36-54
Parent (P4)	Male	7	1501-3000	Secondary	36-54
Parent (P5)	Female	9	1500 TL and	Primary	36-54
Parent (P6)	Male	2	1501-3000	University	36-54
Parent (P7)	Female	10	1500 TL and -	Illiterate	55 and +
Parent (P8)	Male	2	3001 TL and	University	35 and -
Parent (P9)	Male	2	3001 TL and	University	36-54
Parent (P10)	Male	1	3001 TL and	University	36-54
Parent (P11)	Male	4	3001 TL and	High school	36-54
Parent (P12)	Female	3	1500 TL and	Primary	35 and -
Parent (P13)	Female	3	1501-3000 TL	Primary	36-54
Parent (P14)	Female	3	1501-3000 TL	Primary	35 and -
Parent (P15)	Female	-	1501-3000 TL	Secondary	35 and -
Parent (P16)	Female	2	1500 TL and -	Primary	35 and -
Parent (P17)	Female	3	1500 TL and	High school	35 and -
Parent (P18)	Female	4	1500 TL and	Illiterate	35 and -
Parent (P19)	Female	2	3001 TL and	University	35 and -
Parent (P20)	Female	3	1500 TL and	Illiterate	35 and -
Parent (P21)	Female	3	1500 TL and	Secondary	35 and -
Parent (P22)	Female	5	1500 TL and	Primary	35 and -
Parent (P23)	Male	3	3001 TL and -	University	35 and -

Parent (P24)	Female	1	1501-3000 TL	High school	35 and -
Parent (P25)	Female	4	3001 TL and	University	36-54
Parent (P26)	Female	2	3001 TL and	High school	55 and +
Parent (P27)	Male	2	3001 TL and	University	55 and +
Parent (P28)	Female	3	1500 TL and -	Primary	35 and -
Parent (P29)	Female	3	1500 TL and -	Illiterate	35 and -
Parent (P30)	Female	4	1501-300 TL	Primary	35 and -
Parent (P31)	Male	2	1501-300 TL	High school	35 and -
Parent (P32)	Male	1	3001 TL and	University	35 and -
Parent (P33)	Male	2	1501-3000 TL	High school	36-54
Parent (P34)	Female	2	3001 TL and	High school	36-54
Parent (P35)	Female	2	3001 TL and	Secondary	36-54
Parent (P36)	Female	--	3001 TL and	University	35 and -
Parent (P37)	Female	2	3001 TL and	University	35 and -
Parent (P38)	Female	3	1501-3000 TL	High school	35 and -
Parent (P39)	Male	3	1501-3000 TL	Secondary	35 and -
Parent (P40)	Male	2	3001 TL and	High school	35 and -
Parent (P41)	Female	3	1501-3000 TL	University	35 and -
Parent (P42)	Female	1	3001 TL and	University	35 and -
Parent (P43)	Male	1	3001 TL and	University	36-54
Parent (P44)	Male	1	3001 TL and	University	35 and -
Parent (P45)	Female	2	3001 TL and	University	36-54
Parent (P46)	Male	2	3001 TL and	University	35 and -
Parent (P47)	Female	2	3001 TL and	University	35 and -
Parent (P48)	Female	2	3001 TL and	University	35 and -
Parent (P49)	Male	2	3001 TL and	University	36-54

2.4. Data Collection

The preschool, primary, secondary and high schools in the center of Siirt and Batman were visited and the research-related interviews were discussed with the school administrators. One-to-one interviews were conducted in a quiet environment chosen by the school administrators after calling and directing parents to the school and after the appropriate time for the parents was discussed and understood. The responses given during the interview were recorded by the researchers on the interview forms.

2.5. Data Analysis

In the interviews with the parents, the data recorded by the researchers were described and interpreted. In analyzes, the descriptive analysis process was followed. The data were categorized according to their specific characteristics and the cause and effect relationships were tried to be examined and summary information that the reader could easily see was tried to be reached. In the example sentences, the idea of parents is added to the end of the sentence

by shortening (For example, Parent 1 is coded as P1 at the end of the statements). The personal characteristics of the parent can be found in the table under the heading “Study Group (Table 1). In case of parents who have opinions in more than one category, parental statements are exemplified as needed.

3. Findings and Comment

3.1. Why Education?

During the interviews with the parents, the question “Why do you want your child to receive education?” was asked. Although some parents expressed their opinions in more than one category, parents generally expressed their opinions related to the reasons for their children's education in 5 different categories. The responses given by the parents are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Reasons for Education

Codes	<i>f</i>
Economic and Cultural Return	29
Being Useful People	10
Individual Development	19
Protection	2
Obligation	1

29 of the interviewed parents mentioned the economic and cultural returns of education as the reason for their children's education. 10 parents expressed the idea that they receive education to raise their children as a beneficial person for themselves and their environment. 19 stated the necessity of education for the individual development of the student. 2 parents pointed out the protective feature of the education in order to get the child away from the negative factors and 1 parent stated that he had received education because of compulsory education. The parents' statements referring to the economic and cultural returns of education as a reason for the education their children receive are as follows:

So that he can pay for my labor of taking care of him by acquiring any profession (P7). Of course I wish he had a good education. Since our financial situation is not good, we could not get a good education, at least I want my child to have good economic days. Maybe he comes to good places and does not suffer from economic hardship (P12). To get a job, to come to a good place (P13). Education in order to be able to get what they want in life, to be happy with what they have achieved and to learn to stand on their own foot (P8). I want my child to receive basic

education first. This education is important both for my child's development and the future of my child. The education to be provided may be capable of determining the future of the child (P33). 1) To stand on his foot 2) To recognize himself 3) To develop himself in every sense 4) To be a useful individual in society (P37).

The ideas of the parents who propose to train them as useful people are as follows:

I want him to be educated to be a beneficial individual to himself, his family, and society (P25). Education in order to take its place in society and contribute to humanity in living conditions (P27). Knowing the cause of creation, to be a good individual to his country, his family, to live without needing anyone; I want him to be trained to be a good and happy person (P47).

Examples of parents' views that show individual development as reason for education:

Education means knowledge, enlightenment, free and free thinking. For this purpose, the education of the child means that it exists in the past and in the future (P9). To prepare himself a good future for self-sufficiency, to grow as a sensitive individual (P11). Education for the development of the child, development of intelligence, good communication with people (P20). Without education, he would be ignorant, on the streets. He's learning right and good at school. But outside he learns bad and harmful things in the environment (P30). I want him to be an individual who is successful, educated and able to stand on his feet at the level of contemporary civilizations in line with his interests, abilities and demands.

The parents' statement stating that they have to take the education given within the scope of twelve-year compulsory education is as follows:

I am against sending my child to school in the current education system. But I'm sending it out of necessity. I have to send it within the scope of 12 years of compulsory education. Otherwise, we all know that the system educates uniform students and drives people away from life (P19).

3.2. What Kind of Education?

In the answers given to the question “What kind of education do you want your child to receive?” all of the parents stated that the education they wanted their children to exhibit different characteristics in accordance with the contemporary educational approaches (Table 3).

Table 3. The Characteristics of Desired Education

Codes	<i>f</i>
Suitable for Contemporary Education	49

The majority of the parents interviewed wanted to provide education in accordance with contemporary educational approaches and mentioned different dimensions of contemporary educational characteristics. Examples of parents' ideas:

I want him to receive a creative, but without memorization and exam anxiety education (P2). Since my child wants more than necessity, he can get pleasure while doing, away from memorization. I want him to be educated with constructivist training that will appeal to the whole world (P8). I want him to be educated with a constructivist, questioning, thought-provoking and creative understanding of education, not with the existing memorization education (P9). I would like him to receive an education in which he can express himself freely in mutual communication with his teachers and friends (P11). No crowded class, no crowded school. A good teacher should be a good educator. The teacher's behavior is very important and should not offend children (P17). I want an education that will feel free, learn by doing, not stick to books, compete with children, and not based on exams (P19). I want the best in financial means. I want a quality education in accordance with contemporary approaches in a full school equipped with all kinds of physical facilities (P24). I would like my child to undergo a modern and respectful education that will be able to keep up with contemporary scientific developments in a manner that is primarily moral and honest (P31). 1) Disclosure all your skills 2) A quality education 3) I want a contemporary education in which he can apply what he has learned (P37). I would like him to receive the best education in the follow-up of technological developments, which are modern, contemporary, outweighed by the scientific aspect, in line with his wishes and interests, as far as my possibilities are (P45). I want him to be educated in an education system that doesn't put everyone in the same pattern, that rewards effort, not results, that what is important for the student is also important for the school, that the students are guided according to their skills and abilities, that he can apply right law and fairness in real life and that he aims to raise a wounded individual in the society (P49). His education is in a healthy environment, in safe hands, in a respectful and decent environment, and it is enough for the people around him to be an example (P4). It should teach them manners. The school must be clean, tidy. Teachers should treat children as parents (P13). I would like my child to undergo a modern and respectful education that will be able to keep up with

contemporary scientific developments in a manner that is primarily moral and honest (P31). I want him to have an education that is compatible with the values of the society and that can be fully realized without sacrificing science and science (P10).

3.3. Relationship between Welfare Level and Education

Parents were asked “If your welfare level was high, would you still have your child send school after compulsory education? Or would you free your child to go to school or not? Why?. From the 44 parents interviewed, 37 stated that if their economic situation was very good, they would continue their education and would not leave the child to their hearts, and 7 would leave it to the child's choice. Parents' opinions are given in table 4 in these categories.

Table 4. Welfare Level and Education Demand

Codes	Reason	<i>f</i>
Yes, I would have continued education.	Socio-cultural and Economic Return	42
I would leave the choice to the student	Volunteering is Required for Productivity	7

The majority of the parents stated that they would continue their children’s education because of their socio-cultural and economic benefits. The remaining 7 parents stated that the student should be voluntary and willing for efficiency in education and therefore he would leave the choice to the student to continue his education.

Parental statements participating in the interview are as follows:

I would, because it is not possible for a child who does not receive a good education to maintain his well-being in the future (P11). Yes, I would, because the person who does not read is ignorant. I do not want my child to remain ignorant and disconnected from society (P12). Even though I don't have money, I'm sending. I'd send it to better schools. Even though my child didn't want to, I would send. In addition to wealth, he should come to good authorities (P14). I would send him. Education is a must. Without education how would he read, teach and grow up as a good person. I'd give private lessons outside of school. I convince him (P17). Yeah, I certainly would. I wish he was an educated person (P26). Yes, I would. Wealth is separate being able to use wealth is separate. The greatest wealth is to make good use of the possibilities and existing ones. I would force him to read as a parent psychologically (instructive) (P27). I would send him. I want him be equal with his friends. School is different. He has friends, he learns the rules. He knows how to act. It is different for him to start a business with his own labor and find a ready job. I want him to have a job by working (P29). No matter how good you were, I'd

send it to college. Even if he didn't want to go, I'd force him. To be more knowledgeable. What can I do if I'm rich and he's ignorant. It's like flower without water. He's better off coming to his own place. It wouldn't be good for him to come to a place with father's money, ready money. If he doesn't understand the value of life, he doesn't read it all the time (P30). To go to school or not is not my child's initiative. I take steps, even if I have to. I'm one of those people who think that schooling has nothing to do with material. Schooling is essential to being a healthy individual and taking his place in society at this time (P32).

As an example of the statements of the parents who said that I would leave my child the freedom to continue his education:

Of course, I would like my child to study at university and more. But he has to come somewhere voluntarily (P3). I would send him. If he doesn't want, he will be ignorant and unemployed. If he didn't want to go to school, I'd let him go. There is no forced beauty (P15).

3.4. Course Selection and Desired Courses

In the preliminary interviews with teachers and administrators, it was stated that the parents gave more weight to the courses which were found to be equivalent in exams such as Mathematics, Turkish, Science Technology, and Foreign Language. At the same time, depending on the teachers' statements that parents ignore physical development, visual arts and music, which support the personal development of and increase the abilities, the parents are asked “Which lessons do you think your child should take during the education process? Which courses should be focused on?”. Parent responses were divided into 3 categories. Parents' views on this issue are categorically expressed in Table 5.

Table 5. Parent Course Selection and Desired Courses

Codes	<i>f</i>
Courses to be used in exams	24
Suitable courses for his ability to be	14
All courses must be selected	11

Parents' expressions, who want to give weight to the courses encountered in the exams, are as follows:

I want him to take lessons that will make it easier to concentrate on mathematics and make it easier to be assigned in the future (P7). Turkish, Mathematics, Social are important to me. The painting and music is less important. Maths and Turkish lessons should be given the most

because they take place in the exam (P22). Basic courses in mathematics and Turkish. They are popular in the country (P26). My daughter (Grade 8) and my son (Grade 3) especially want to take Mathematics and Turkish lessons. For me it is the foundation of the profession. I don't want to focus on lessons like painting. Because if he / she works for these courses, he / she will pass the exam and the other courses do not contribute to the exam (P28). Mathematics, philosophy, history, chemistry, physics and language classes. Science and foreign language should be given weight; as a result they will appear in exams (P31).

Examples of parents' opinions who want to focus on the courses that improve student skills that are appropriate for the student's ability are as follows:

I want him to take the appropriate courses such as painting and music (P2). Turkish to express himself; geography and history to know his past; physical education classes for physical health and a healthy life (P9). Apart from the Social Sciences and Science courses, I would like my child to choose his / her elective courses according to his / her abilities and skills (P49).

The statements of the parents who want to focus on the courses that will be useful both for exams and in the process of acquiring the profession are as follows:

Basic lessons such as Turkish and mathematics, where both physical skills are predominant and to sustain life, should be emphasized (P11). He has to take all the lessons to improve himself. Especially the exams such as Mathematics and Turkish are also important (P15).

The statements of the parents who want to think in a multi-dimensional way and to give weight to all courses are as follows:

Mathematics, Science, Social Sciences, Arabic, English, Literature, Quran, Hadith, all courses should be given. I would like him to take courses in various artistic and sportive fields in line with his talent. All courses should be balanced and weighted according to the area of interest (P46). Literature, Philosophy, Logic, Mathematics, Religious sciences, History I think he should see a piece of all courses. But most importantly, it should be given an educational environment in which life can be seen and understood (P47).

3.5. Future Dream and the Right to Choose a department

The parents are asked “Do you have a future dream for your child? Would you release your child to choose a department at the university?” and parents' opinions are given in table 6 in categories.

Table 6. Parents' Future Dreams and Children's Choice

Codes	<i>f</i>
I have a dream - I will release him	22
I have no future dream - We decide together	14
I have no future dream - I will release him	3
I have a future dream - I will not release him	10

The parents' opinions who have dreams about their children's future; but they will release their child about the selection of departments during the university entrance exam are as follows:

Of course there is. I let him choose his department at the university because his profession will be an important part of life and I don't want him to live an unhappy life (P11). I want him to be a doctor. But let him choose a profession he has studied (P16). We give up our dreams based on our current life due to country conditions. My dream and my son's dream is same; to be astronaut. However, as soon as time shows, I release it if it wants something over time (P19). I want him to be a judge or a prosecutor, he's against the injustices. He will go to school, so I release him (P24).

As an example of parents' opinions who have no future dreams and that they will decide together with their child over time:

I have no dreams for the future. My daughter is better in verbal classes. I would like him to choose a branch to decide for herself. Of course, if I want, I can direct. My son is a different child. It may be more successful in engineering or technology. I do the same in his choice of profession (P45). Frankly, I don't have a dream about the profession. I mean, I can't tell my kid to go to that job. After having a good education and a solid personality, let him be an individual with a strong spiritual aspect and a good mental and physical health. He has a firm stance against life and finds a suitable profession for himself. I definitely release him about university (P46).

As an example of the parents' opinions who have no future dream and that they will decide on the department that his / her child will go:

I have no dreams for the future. I will certainly release it because I believe that if our child does what he loves, he will be beneficial to society (P6). I never thought about it, I set him free on the university and I accept his decision (P15). No. I didn't dream. I will guide him if he wants, we decide together (P16).

As an example of the parents' opinions who have a future dream about their child and that they will not release their child about the department their children will go in the future:

I send them to medical school; if they won't want they won't go. If the profession is something I don't want, I won't let him do it (P13). He could be a lawyer. I will not release my kid. I do not let him go to school useless (P23). No, I wouldn't let him. I would like him to be a teacher or a lawyer (P26). No, I won't let him free; he could be a lawyer (P41).

4. Conclusion and Discussion

The aim of this study is to reveal the parents' perceptions and expectations of education based on their own statements. In accordance with the principle of easy accessibility, data were collected by conducting interviews with 49 parents who had students in schools in different socio-economic environments and the data were analyzed and presented through descriptive analysis. The research results are as follows:

The parents were asked the question “Why Education?” to reveal the reasons for their children's education. More than half of the parents stated the economic and cultural benefits of education as the reason for their children's education. Then, the prominent ideas are; individual development, upbringing a beneficial person for himself and the environment; the protective features of education and school. Also a mother who graduated from university, declared the idea of compulsory education. When parents' statements were examined, less than half of the parents interviewed stated the reason for their children's education as individual development and raising a useful person.

When the literature was examined, it was found that family expectations about the educational success of the child had a significant effect on the success of the child (Jacob and Wilder, 2010; Smyth, 2018; Froiland, and Davison, 2014; Fan and Chen, 2001; Seginer, 1983; Hill and Taylor, 2004). Delprato (2019) states that parental expectations have an effect on the formation and transition of educational expectations for children learning. Zimmermann and Williams, (2016) have found that high parental expectations are positively related with students' academic achievement. The success of children increases significantly, especially when educational expectations between parents and children are similar (Hao and Bonstead-Bruns, 1998). Zhang, (2014) claims that child academic self-concepts and feelings of disengagement have effects on child educational expectations and achievements.

Research has shown that in addition to providing good communication at school, parental involvement providing home support, encouragement and direct education improves students' school performance (Mau, 1997). It is determined that the most important factors affecting the success of the school is that families spend time for their children, read to the child and love them unconditionally (Flores, 2016). According to the results of the research in the literature, teachers, administrators and policy makers acknowledge the effect of parental involvement on student academic achievement (Wilder, 2014). In this respect, it can be said that parents' expectations are an important factor in the development of children.

As a result of the field study conducted by Can, (2015) the parents' expectations from primary and secondary schools have been revealed that the child is having a social and good communication skills, self-confidence and responsibility, character and self-realization, settling in a secondary education institution providing quality education and having a good profession. Accordingly, it is possible to say that economic and social returns are at the forefront of the expectations of families from education. As a matter of fact, Coombs and Ahmed (1974) state that education is seen as an instrument of economic return and productivity in developing countries. Similarly, Bozyiğit (2017) found that the most important factor that parents take into consideration when choosing a school is the academic achievement of the teacher and the school. Bakioğlu and Bahçeci, (2010) also showed that parents' views on school image were based on exam success. According to Çokgezen and Erdene (2015), as the level of education increases, individuals have higher human capital equipment, work in jobs requiring more qualifications and earn higher earnings. As Do and Mancillas, (2006) state that among the educational expectations that children had for themselves, high-achieving children had higher educational expectations than the low-achieving children. Therefore it can be claimed that the educational expectations of parents and children are important factors in predicting children's educational achievements and occupational outcomes (Yu and Daraganova, 2015).

The findings of the studies in the literature support the finding of this research that “parents prioritize the economic and cultural returns of education”. In this context, it can be claimed that the primary expectations of parents from education are economic benefits such as finding a good job, earning money and prosperity through education.

When the parents were asked what kind of education should be given to their children, all of the parents stated that the education they wanted to be given to their children should exhibit contemporary features and touched different components of contemporary education. Prior

research has shown that parents' educational expectations contribute positively to several student academic outcomes, including grades in school, standardized test scores, and school completion (Huguley, Kyere, & Wang, 2018). According to Güleş and Erişen (2013), parents expect education to raise their children in the ways required by the information age. According to the results of the research conducted by Nartgün and Kaya (2016), an ideal school for parents has these features such as; taking into consideration the individual interests and abilities of the students, taking into consideration the artistic and sporting activities of the students, revealing their social development, giving importance to academic development with knowledge and equipment, effectively teaching at least one foreign language, children can be entrusted with confidence and provide rich material support. Smyth, (2018) states that parents appear to rely on a number of signals, including academic achievement, disengagement from maths, ability group allocation and teacher reprimands, from the school system in shaping their view of their children's potential. The strong social structuring of parental expectations has potentially significant implications for young people's outcomes. When these issues are taken into consideration, it can be said that the parents emphasize the contemporary features of school education.

In terms of welfare level and education, the majority of the parents stated that they would continue their children's education after compulsory education even if their welfare level is very good and that they would not leave the preference to the student. Only seven of the forty-nine parents interviewed stated that they would leave the choice to their child as they considered volunteering as a condition for education. According to this, parents state that even though their economic welfare levels are high, they want their children to receive education.

Research in the literature shows that education, especially non-formal education, is an appropriate model for developing countries and has a positive effect on poverty reduction (Çokgezen and Erdene, 2015). Similarly, in the field research conducted by Can, (2015), the parents expect their children get high scores from exams and gain a high school and have a good profession as a result; they also expect that their personality and character will develop positively and grow up as a social individual. In this case, parents want their children to continue their education by prioritizing the economic and socio-cultural benefits of education for their children even if their welfare levels are high. Huguley, Kyere, and Wang, (2018) found that African American parents' short-term expectations for performance (i.e., grades in school) impact their children's academic success. Moreover Do and Mancillas, (2006) demonstrated the importance of educational expectations upon student achievement and the tendency for low

socioeconomic status (SES) and Latino students to perform academically at lower levels than higher SES students.

About the course selection and desired courses for the students, almost half of the parents stated that the courses that should be given to the students should be the courses that will contribute to the exams. This result coincides with the expressions of parents who do not leave their choice of continuing education to their children even if the welfare level of the majority is good. In other words, parents see education as a prospective investment tool. As a matter of fact, in the study conducted by Can, (2015), the expectations of parents from primary and secondary schools were stated as “settling in a secondary education institution providing high quality education and having a good profession”. Coombs and Ahmed (1974) state that education is seen as an instrument of economic returns and productivity in developing countries. Similarly, Bozyiğit (2017) found that the most important factor that parents take into consideration when choosing a school is the academic achievement of the teacher and the school. Bakioğlu and Bahçeci, (2010) also showed that parents' views on school image were based on exam success. According to Çokgezen and Erdene (2015), as the level of education increases, individuals have higher human capital equipment, work in jobs requiring more qualifications and earn higher earnings. Thus education improves living standards by increasing personal earnings. PISA data shows that 15-year-old students' expectations for completing a university-level programme are closely associated with their performance in mathematics and reading. Within every OECD country, students' expectations for their educational attainment rise with their performance level in mathematics and reading (OECD, 2007).

Parents' opinions about the courses to be taught in schools in terms of “choosing the courses that will be used in the exams” reveals that they have expectations from education and exams and academic success. This reinforces the view that the basic expectations of parents in education are economic returns in our country.

Two thirds of the parents stated that they had a future dream about their children and about one fifth stated that they would not release their children in the selection of departments in higher education. There are only three parents who state that they do not have a dream about the future of their child and that they will release their child in the selection of the department. Accordingly, parents are interested in the education of their children; they have dreams about their future and are actively involved in deciding their child's career choice.

When the literature is examined, Fan and Chen (2001) showed that there is a positive relationship between parental participation and expectation and student achievement through meta-analysis. Toldson and Lemmons, (2013) found that parents' participation in school and positive practices of the family had a positive effect on students' success. Accordingly, it is seen that family participation is one of the important variables explaining student achievement (Toprakçı and Gülmez, 2018). In the same way, the lack of family support and the lack of care of the parents were found to be the factors preventing success in education (Demirtaş and Çınar, 2004; Tösten, Han and Ergül, 2016). On the other hand parents' higher educational expectations for adolescents were positively related to their children's life satisfaction, self-esteem, and educational attainment (Jung, Hwang, Zhang, and Zhang, 2018). Accordingly, it is desirable for parents to have dreams about their children's future and to actively participate in their education. However, it is clear that it is not appropriate to insist on intervening in the choice of profession of children and to impose their own wishes and expectations on children rather than the wishes and abilities of the child.

In general, it can be stated that parents' expectations and demands of education do not match. In other words, while the expectations of the parents were more idealized, their demands were directed towards reality. Although parents state that they have educational expectations in line with contemporary educational approaches, it can be stated that they adopt and demand practices that are incompatible with contemporary approaches both philosophically and in educational approaches. In the answer to the question of “what kind of education?” the parents stated the expectation of contemporary education approaches however, in the answer to the question of “why education?” the parents have taken into account the economic and cultural benefits of education, a small part of them mentioned individual development. For example, a parent stated about her child's future dreams and the choice of department in higher education that he can be a lawyer; I'm not releasing my kid. I will not let him go to school useless (P23)”. When he stated “go to school useless” he described the aspect of education as a means of gaining occupation and thus providing economic benefit. He stated that it would be more appropriate if he could make money by acquiring a profession; therefore he ignored the two main aims of education such as individualization and socialization. According to this parent's statement (university graduate, male, under the age of 35), it means that if education does not provide benefits such as occupation and economic return, getting education does not make sense. This reveals that parents want the education to be in line with contemporary approaches at the expectation point, but that the requested education should serve socio-economic welfare

rather than modernity. It is argued by the majority of the parents that even if their welfare levels are good due to their socioeconomic returns, they will continue their children's education after compulsory education and that the continuity of socio-economic welfare can be guaranteed by education. Again, the majority of the parents' the preference of choosing for their children the courses which will be used in the exams can be expressed as an indicator of this situation. However, the aim of contemporary educational approaches is not only to prepare the child for national examinations, but to ensure the multi-dimensional development of the individual.

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